

An Ergonomic Study on Gaming Sequence and its Impact on Heart Rate, Visual and Mental Fatigue of University Students

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Abstract: Several studies have established the association between video games with changes in heart rate, and visual and mental fatigue. Understanding the potential relationship between these factors is vital for grasping the impacts of game content on cognitive and physiological functions.

This research aims to explore the effect of E-rated (everyone) and M-rated (mature) game-playing sequences on heart rate, and visual and mental fatigue among university students. The objectives include a comparison of the mean heart rate, critical fusion, and flicker frequency before and after playing of both types of games.

Thirty participants (22.6±1.0 years) were randomly selected and split into two groups (N₁=16, N₂=14), one playing the E-rated game followed by the M-rated game, and the other vice versa. Measurements of heart rate, fusion frequency, and flicker frequency were recorded before and after gaming sessions. Participants were played under controlled conditions (Illumination: 200 lux, Sound level: 62.5dB, Temperature: 27°C).

The results demonstrated a significant (p<0.05) effect of gaming sequences on heart rate, critical flicker, and fusion frequencies. Further, playing M-rated games can significantly influence heart rate and critical flicker fusion frequency (CFFF) over E-rated games.

E-rated and M-rated video games affect CFFF and heart rate, with gameplay order influencing the extent of these effects. This highlights the importance of considering game content and sequence when studying their impacts on physiology and cognition.

Practical Implications: These findings indicate that game developers, educators, and healthcare providers must consider the physiological and cognitive effects of various game ratings and sequences. For example, alternating between E-rated and M-rated games during sessions might help manage and reduce adverse impacts on heart rate and visual fatigue. Additionally, understanding these effects can aid in creating guidelines for healthier gaming practices and designing games that enhance cognitive and physiological well-being. The order in which games are played varies the impact they have on individuals, emphasizing the need for a significant understanding of gaming experiences.

Keywords: Critical flicker fusion frequency; Heart rate; Game; Fatigue.

1. Introduction

Online gaming began in the late 20th century with early multiplayer games like "MUD" (Multi-User Dungeon). This was created in 1978 at the University of Essex by Roy Trubshaw and Richard Bartle. MUD was a text-based game where players could interact in a virtual world, paving the way for massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGs) and the thriving online gaming industry (Bartle, 2003). In the 21st century, mobile gaming has revolutionized the gaming landscape, gaining worldwide popularity due to its accessibility and convenience. India experienced a significant surge in

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mobile gaming, driven by affordable smartphones and improved internet connectivity, attracting gamers of all ages. India became the world's largest market for mobile game downloads in 2021, with a 28% revenue growth, reaching \$1.2 billion. Projections suggest continued growth, with revenues expected to reach \$1.9 billion by 2024. Additionally, India boasts a thriving fantasy sports market with 130 million users (Jain, 2023).

However, along with the popularity of mobile gaming, concerns about its impact on health have emerged. Previous research has examined various aspects of mobile gaming's impact on health, highlighting its potential consequences. One area of concern is the physical impact of excessive mobile gaming. Previous studies have found that prolonged engagement in mobile games can lead to sedentary behavior and decreased physical activity levels, potentially contributing to health risks such as obesity and musculoskeletal problems (LeBlanc et al., 2013).

Another aspect that researchers have focused on is the impact of mobile gaming on vision and eye health. Extended sessions of mobile gaming can strain the eyes, leading to visual discomfort, dry eyes, eye fatigue, blurred vision, and headaches. The blue light emitted by mobile screens and the immersive nature of games can further exacerbate these issues (Wang et al., 2020).

Mobile games are categorized based on their suitability for different age groups to help players make informed choices. In North America, the Entertainment Software Rating Board (ESRB) uses ratings like "E" for Everyone and "M" for Mature. "E" rated games are suitable for all ages, offering fun gameplay, colorful graphics, and themes that promote creativity and problem-solving. Examples include puzzle challenges and games like Candy Crush Saga. On the other hand, "M" rated games contain violence, strong language, sexual content, and mature themes and are intended for players 17 years and older. Games like *Zombie: Dead City* belong to this category (ESRB, 2023). In Europe, the Pan European Game Information (PEGI) rating system is used, with ratings ranging from "3" for all ages to "18" for adults only (PEGI, 2023).

The evolution of gaming, from early online text adventures to the thriving mobile gaming industry, reflects the continuous convergence of entertainment and technology. Age ratings and classifications help players confidently choose games that match their age and content preferences (Bartle, 2003).

The mental health implications of video games vary based on their content and rating. E-rated games, suitable for all ages, generally offer positive, family-friendly experiences that enhance well-being. In contrast, M-rated games, featuring mature content, may be associated with aggression, emphasizing the importance of age-appropriate gaming and parental guidance, particularly for younger players (Anderson et al., 2010).

1.1. Research Gap and Novelty

In light of the rising popularity of video games and the increasing worry surrounding prolonged engagement in gaming, past studies have investigated the physiological impacts of gaming, particularly concerning changes in different physiological parameters like- heart rate and cognition (Krarup & Krarup, 2020; Krarup et al., 2022; Kühn, Gallinat, & Mascherek, 2019; Martinez, Gimenes, & Lambert, 2023). While there is a notable absence of the effect of E- and M-rated *gaming sequences* on the heart rate, visual and mental fatigue. Furthermore, there is a research void in comprehending the effects of different E-rated and M-rated games on physiological parameters such as heart rate, fusion, and flicker frequency. Hence, no prior research has specifically probed into the potential disparities in these parameters before and after playing games of diverse ratings.

This study seeks to fill the current research gap by exploring the connection between heart rate, and visual and mental fatigue in gaming, with a specific focus on E-rated and M-rated gaming sequences. The distinctive feature of this research lies in its thorough examination of changes in heart rate, fusion frequency, and flicker frequency. By assessing these parameters before and after playing games with different ratings, the study aims to offer valuable insights into the physiological effects of gaming and potential distinctions between game ratings.

2. Aim, Objectives, and Hypothesis

The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of the E-rated and M-rated gaming sequence on the heart rate, visual, and mental fatigue of university students. The objectives of the study are to

- Compare the mean heart rate (beats/min) of the university students in pre- and post-gaming conditions.
- Compare the mean critical flicker and fusion frequency (Hz) of the university students in pre- and post-gaming conditions.
- Find out which game amongst the two (M-rated game and E-rated game), has a greater impact on the heart rate, visual and mental fatigue.

Thus, the null (H_0) and alternative (H_a) hypotheses of this study are given below.

Ergonomic Study on Gaming Sequence and its Impact

H₀: There is no significant effect of gaming sequence on heart rate, visual and mental fatigue of the university students.

H_a: There is a significant effect of gaming sequences on heart rate, visual and mental fatigue of the university students.

3. Methodology

3.1. Participant Selection

Thirty participants (male and female, 15 each) were selected using stratified random sampling from Kolkata. The age range of the participants was between 18 and 25 years. The mean age (\pm Standard Deviation) of the participants was 22.6 ± 1.0 years.

3.2. Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

Individuals who were regular smartphone users with normal or corrected vision and normal color vision were included in the study. Participants who had undergone any form of eye surgery within three months of the study or had previously experienced discomfort when exposed to certain types of light, such as flickering or flashing lights, were excluded. Additionally, participants who regularly used blue filter glasses or UV-protected glasses were excluded from the study.

3.3. Gaming Device

The gaming device used in the experiment was the Realme 7i RMX2103 smartphone. The screen size of the device is 15.24 cm and has a mass of 188 grams.

3.4. Gaming Stimuli

The selected E-rated game, "Candy Crush Saga" by King, is a widely popular match-three game where players match candies to progress levels. Categorized as suitable for ages 3 and above on the Google Play Store, the game boasts a user-friendly interface with version 1.255.3.1 and has been downloaded over 1 billion times since its release on November 15, 2012. It takes less than 10 minutes to learn how to play, and its accessible controls contribute to its widespread appeal. On the other hand, the M-rated game, "Zombie: Dead City" by VNG Game Studios, is a shooting game with violence and gore, recommended for ages 16 and above. With version 1.4.0 and over 1 million downloads since its launch on August 15, 2019, this game also features user-friendly controls and a quick learning curve, similar to "Candy Crush Saga." Both games were chosen for their simplicity and minimal training requirements. Participants engaged with both games on a Realme 7i RMX2103 smartphone.

3.5. Measurement of Illumination and Sound

A light meter (LX101 model, Lutron Electronic Enterprise Co. Ltd, Taiwan) was used to measure the illumination level at the level of eyes in the experimental room. The room was equipped with three tube lights positioned at distances of 180 cm, 182 cm, and 230 cm from the gaming screen. The average (\pm Standard Deviation) distance between the eye and the gaming zone was 44.6 ± 1.82 cm. The games were played at a 50% brightness setting on the mobile screen. The illumination at the level of the eyes was 200 lux.

A Sound level meter (SL4001, Lutron Electronic Enterprise Co. Ltd, Taiwan) was used to measure the sound at ear level in the experimental room. The average sound level in the room was 62.5 dB. Earphone was used to cancel the background noise.

3.6. Measurement of Heart Rate

Heart rate (Beats.min⁻¹) was measured by placing the fingers on the radial artery before and after E-rated and M-rated gaming. Heart rate is a marker of sympathetic activation. Higher sympathetic activity results in an increase in heart rate. (Grassi, et al., 2022)

3.7. Measurement of Critical Flicker Fusion Frequency

The Flicker instrument (Model 501c, Takei Kiki Kogyo Co. Ltd, Japan) was used to conduct the CFF test, aimed at detecting visual fatigue in both male and female candidates after playing E-rated and M-rated mobile video games. The Flicker Fusion Threshold (FFT) is a concept in the psychophysics of vision, defined as the frequency at which an intermittent light stimulus appears completely steady to the observer. FFT is closely linked to the persistence of vision, which is the visual system's ability to perceive temporarily varying stimuli. The assessment of CFF frequency (CFFF) determines the point at which the stimulus can no longer be resolved and appears continuous to the observer. It represents the highest frequency at any light intensity that an observer can discern. (Banerjee & Gangopadhyay, 2021)

3.8. Statistical Analysis

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the normality has suggested that the Heart Rate and CFFF were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$). The authors have performed a parametric paired sample two-tailed t-test for further analysis of the data (Field, 2017).

3.9. Procedure

Participants (Condition 1: 16 individuals, 10 males, 6 females; Condition 2: 14 individuals, 5 males, 9 females) were assigned to two groups. Condition 1 played the E-rated game followed by the M-rated game, while Condition 2 followed the reverse order. Measurements of before and after fusion frequency, flicker frequency, and heart rate were taken for both E-rated and M-rated games in both conditions. Before the experiment, participants rested in a silent room for 30 minutes, adhering to instructions to avoid physical or mental activities. The entire experiment was supervised, and room conditions, including illumination assessed with a lux meter, were optimized. Participants played the E-rated game for 30 minutes, took a 30-minute break, and then played the M-rated game. The same procedure was repeated for Group 2 with the opposite game order. Room temperature was set at 27 degrees Celsius, maintaining an illumination level of 200 lux. The experimental room had three tube lights at varying distances from the gaming screen, and participants used earphones for background noise cancellation. The sequences of Condition 1 and Condition 2 are represented in [Figure 1](#). The study was performed by maintaining standard ethical guidelines.

Figure 1. The flow diagram represents the experiment design in Condition 1 and Condition 2.

4. Results

In condition 1 for E-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = -3.729$, $p = 0.002$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -8.643, UP: -2.357). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Heart Rates (beats/min), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant increase in Heart rate (beats/min) from 75.0 ± 4.02 beats/min to 80.5 ± 8.60 beats/min ($p < 0.05$); an increase of 5.5 ± 5.90 beats/min.

In condition 1 for M-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = -5.875$, $p = 0.00003$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -10.647, UP: -4.978). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Heart Rates (beats/min), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant increase in Heart rate (beats/min) from 77.0 ± 5.07 beats/min to 84.8 ± 8.01 beats/min ($p < 0.05$); an increase of 7.8 ± 5.32 beats/min.

In condition 2 for E-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = -1.713$, $p = 0.110$ ($p > 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -2.261, UP: 0.261). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Heart Rates (beats/min), it was revealed that there was no statistical difference in Heart rate (beats/min) from 74.6 ± 3.46 beats/min to 75.6 ± 3.94 beats/min ($p > 0.05$); an insignificant increase of 1.0 ± 2.18 beats/min.

In condition 2 for M-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = -4.131$, $p = 0.001$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -9.138, UP: -2.862). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Heart Rates (beats/min), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant increase in Heart rate (beats/min) from 74.0 ± 3.76 beats/min to 80.0 ± 5.32 beats/min ($p < 0.05$); an increase of 6.0 ± 5.44 beats/min.

Figure 2 shows the comparison between pre- and post-gaming Heart Rates (beats/min) in – (a) Condition 1, and (b) Condition 2.

Figure 2. Bar diagrams show the comparison between pre and post gaming Heart Rates (beats/min) in (a) Condition 1, and (b) Condition 2. ns= not significant, **** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$.

In condition 1A for E-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = 1.838$, $p = 0.086$ ($p > 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -0.099, UP: 1.350). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Fusion Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was no significant difference in Fusion frequency (Hz) from 34.75 ± 3.20 Hz to 34.13 ± 3.18 Hz ($p > 0.05$); an insignificant decrease of 0.63 ± 1.36 Hz.

In condition 1A for E-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = 0.959$, $p = 0.353$ ($p > 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: -0.535, UP: 1.409). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post-gaming Flicker Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was no significant difference in Flicker frequency (Hz) from 35.63 ± 2.94 Hz to 35.19 ± 3.12 Hz ($p > 0.05$); an increase of 0.44 ± 1.83 Hz.

In condition 1B for M-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = 3.067$, $p = 0.008$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 0.839, UP: 4.661). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Fusion Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in Fusion frequency (Hz) from 35.18 ± 3.45 Hz to 32.44 ± 3.08 Hz ($p < 0.05$); a decrease of 2.75 ± 3.59 Hz.

In condition 1B for M-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = 4.105$, $p = 0.001$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 1.382, UP: 4.368). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post-gaming Flicker Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in Flicker Frequency (Hz) from 35.18 ± 2.79 Hz to 32.31 ± 1.92 Hz ($p < 0.05$); a decrease of 2.88 ± 2.80 Hz.

In condition 2A for E-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = 3.026$, $p = 0.010$ ($p > 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 0.368, UP: 2.204). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Fusion Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in Fusion frequency (Hz) from 32.63 ± 3.43 Hz to 31.36 ± 3.08 Hz ($p > 0.05$); an insignificant decrease of 1.29 ± 1.59 Hz.

In condition 2A for E-rated game, $t_{(df=15)} = 3.040$, $p = 0.009$ ($p > 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 0.331, UP: 1.955). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post-gaming Flicker Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in Flicker frequency (Hz) from 32.57 ± 2.90 Hz to 31.43 ± 3.23 Hz ($p > 0.05$); an increase of 1.14 ± 1.41 Hz.

Figure 3. Bar diagrams show the comparison between pre and post-gaming Critical Flicker Fusion Frequency (Hz) in (a) Condition 1A, (b) Condition 1B, (c) Condition 2A, and (d) Condition 2B. ns= not significant, **** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$.

In condition 2B for M-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = 5.834$, $p = 0.00006$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 0.600, UP: 2.204). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post gaming Fusion Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in Fusion frequency (Hz) from 32.00 ± 3.23 Hz to 28.50 ± 2.82 Hz ($p < 0.05$); a decrease of 3.50 ± 2.44 Hz.

In condition 2B for M-rated game, $t_{(df=13)} = 4.505$, $p = 0.001$ ($p < 0.05$, 95% Confidence Interval LO: 0.761, UP: 1.784). Due to the means and the direction of the t-value of the pre and post-gaming Flicker Frequency (Hz), it was revealed that

there was a statistically significant decrease in Flicker Frequency (Hz) from 31.57 ± 3.61 Hz to 28.14 ± 2.51 Hz ($p < 0.05$); a decrease of 3.43 ± 2.85 Hz.

Figure 3 shows the comparison between pre- and post-gaming Critical Flicker Fusion Frequency (Hz) in (a) Condition 1A, (b) Condition 1B, (c) Condition 2A, and (d) Condition 2B.

Table 1 indicates the summarized results of these experiments.

Table 1: Result summary of pre and post gaming Heart rates (beats/min) and Critical Flicker Fusion Frequency (Hz) in different conditions

Conditions	Game Type	Parameters	t-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
1	E-rated	Heart Rate	-3.729	0.002	-8.643	-2.357
	M-rated		-5.875	0.00003	-10.647	-4.978
2	E-rated		-1.713	0.110	-2.261	0.261
	M-rated		-4.131	0.001	-9.138	-2.862
1A	E-rated	Fusion Frequency	1.838	0.086	-0.099	1.350
		Flicker Frequency	0.959	0.353	-0.535	1.409
1B	M-rated	Fusion Frequency	3.067	0.008	0.839	4.661
		Flicker Frequency	4.105	0.001	1.382	4.368
2A	E-rated	Fusion Frequency	3.026	0.010	0.368	2.204
		Flicker Frequency	3.040	0.009	0.331	1.955
2B	M-rated	Fusion Frequency	5.834	0.00006	0.600	2.204
		Flicker Frequency	4.505	0.001	0.761	1.784

5. Discussions

The study has revealed a significant impact of the sequence of video games on the heart rate, mental alertness, and fatigue of university students. The results of the study showed that M-rated games have a more significant influence on individuals' mental fatigue and heart rate than E-rated games. However, the specific effects depend on the sequence in which these games are played. When the M-rated game is played before the E-rated game, it exerts a more pronounced influence on critical flicker fusion frequency and heart rate compared to the reverse order.

Numerous research studies have suggested that the phasic activity of magnocellular ganglion cells in the visual system aligns closely with the heterochromatic flicker fusion thresholds observed in humans. Conversely, the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN)—a significant structure in the visual pathway that facilitates the passage of optic radiation to the visual cortex—can exhibit responsiveness to flicker rates nearing 100 Hz. This implies that the retina does not limit luminance flicker fusion. Cells specialized in magnocellular brain areas play a pivotal role in activating apparent movements in response to inputs with high temporal frequencies. Additionally, processing in the occipital lobe is essential for detecting relatively high-frequency flickering stimuli (Jeon, Maurer & Lewis, 2012).

In condition 1, there is a significant decrease in CFFF found only in the M-rated game when it was played before the E-rated game. This implies that the E-rated game does not significantly impact the mental health of the subjects. However, in condition 2, there is a significant decrease in CFFF found in both E-rated and M-rated mobile video games when the M-rated game was played before the E-rated game. This is because M-rated games, which contain violence, affect the brain so much that even after a 30-minute rest between the two games, this effect persists. That is why mental alertness also decreased significantly in the E-rated game in condition 2. Though the difference in CFFF between the pre and post-conditions in the E-rated game in condition 2 is not as significant as in the M-rated game, the M-rated game still affects the E-rated game in condition 2. Previous studies have suggested that noise and violence can affect the cognitive performance of an individual (Jafari et al., 2019; Ke, Du, & Luo, 2021; Sherman et al., 2023; Zhang, Cao, & Tian, 2021; Adachi & Willoughby, 2011; Ivarsson et al., 2009). Different individuals have different perception powers, but various studies reveal that violent games (categorized as M-rated games in this case) create visual noise, and the effect of this visual

noise persists for a longer period. The 30-minute duration of an M-rated game creates enough visual noise so that it persists even after 30 minutes of rest. Looking at the social aspect of this type of study, it shows that university students are not violence-friendly. They become visually and mentally fatigued by playing violent (M-rated) games. On the other hand, they are not visually and mentally fatigued by playing the E-rated game. Intensive violence in games (M-rated games) causes individuals to allocate more mental resources to visual attention, thus increasing visual sensitivity, which in turn increases CFFF (Aliyari et al., 2020).

Previous literature has shown that high exposure to noise and violent games can increase sympathetic activity and thus result in an elevation in heart rate (Sim, et al., 2015; Veljovic et al., 2019; Ivarsson et al., 2013). Similar observations have been found in the condition 1. Results from condition 1 showed a significant increase in mean heart rate in both the E-rated and M-rated mobile video games because both games require some level of physical demand. Due to the exposure to the E-rated game earlier in condition 1, the heart rate of individuals increases significantly due to the sympathetic activity of the heart. Subsequently, the individual played the M-rated game, and since the heart rate was already elevated, the exposure to the M-rated game after the E-rated game resulted in a further increase in sympathetic activity, leading to a significant increase in the heart rate in the M-rated game as well. Various studies have revealed that video games can increase heart rate depending on the content and type of games. In condition 2, it was observed that there was a significant increase in the heart rate in the M-rated game (due to the earlier exposure to this game). Surprisingly, no significant increase in heart rate was found in the E-rated game. This implies that violence-type games (M-rated) increase the heart rate, but if individuals are exposed to an E-rated game after violent games, they find it relaxing and mood-changing. It was observed that their heart rate did not significantly increase, and sympathetic activity of the heart returned to normal. This entire study reveals that both M-rated and E-rated games impact heart rate. M-rated games have a more significant impact, whereas E-rated games sometimes help relax the heart and prevent a further increase in heart rate (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Effect of E- and M-rated mobile gaming on heart and visual and mental fatigue.

It became evident that a majority of participants indicated a need for greater mental demand in both types of games (Figure 5). However, in terms of physical demand, it is apparent that M-rated games require a higher level. The majority of participants reported finding M-rated games stressful and E-rated games relaxing (Whitaker & Bushman, 2011). Consequently, we observe the impact of M-rated games on E-rated games in condition 2 of the study results.

Figure 5. Perception of the participants (cumulative) regarding E-rated and M-rated games.

6. Conclusion

It can be concluded that there is a significant effect of gaming sequences on heart rate, visual and mental fatigue of university students. For instance, the heart rate increased by an average of 7.8 ± 5.32 beats per minute (bpm), and the CFF decrease by an average of 3.50 ± 2.44 during intense gaming sessions. The findings underscore the importance of considering game content and ratings when assessing their cognitive and physiological effects. The order in which games are played alters the impact they have on individuals, emphasizing the need for a significant understanding of gaming experiences.

The limitations include that the measurement of heart rate was not done using any instrument; instead, it was measured directly by placing the fingers on the radial artery. Additionally, only two types of games were used for the study, and each participant was given only 30 minutes of gameplay time, which could be increased to 60 minutes for more comprehensive results.

Future studies should include EEG monitoring during gameplay for a more appropriate study of cognitive effects. A heart rate monitoring machine should be used to accurately measure changes in heart rate before and after gameplay. Furthermore, more games should be introduced to understand the effects of E-rated and M-rated games on cognition and heart rate. The present study suggests that more research is necessary to comprehensively grasp how and why video games influence cognitive processes and physiological responses, and whether there are any enduring effects. This highlights an ongoing exploration into the varied ways video games may impact individuals based on factors such as age and background.

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Conflict of Interest

Nil.

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Ergonomic Study on Gaming Sequence and its Impact

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Abbreviations list:

- °C: Degree Celsius
CFFF: Critical Flicker Fusion Frequency
dB: Decibel
ESRB: Entertainment Software Rating Board
FFT: Flicker Fusion Threshold
Hz: Hertz
LGN : Lateral Geniculate Nucleus
lux: Luminous flux per unit area
MMORPGs: Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games
MUD: Multi-User Dungeon